

Towards the Elaboration of a Framework to Quantify the Level of Usability and User Experience of Learning Support Platforms

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Abstract. Considering aspects that can guarantee a pleasant experience and the user's final satisfaction are currently the main concerns of the software development teams. The software industry is in search of products that, besides implement the correct and expected functionality, provide a satisfying interaction for users to achieve their goals. Software systems in the educational domain are not an exception. Verifying if the application is usable, as well as, accrediting that the system support, in fact, the teaching and learning processes, are essential aspects for the obtaining of a high-quality product. In this paper, the authors describe the results of a systematic literature review that aimed to identify the fundamental elements that must be considered in the design of software tools that support educational processes. This research has served as a basis to subsequently formulate a preliminary framework that can be used by professionals in the field of Human-Computer Interaction to evaluate the usability, UX and the orientation to the educational domain.

Keywords: Human-Computer Interaction, Systematic review, Usability, User experience, Heuristic evaluation, Education.

1 Introduction

The evolution of technology in the last few years is a big opportunity for organizations to make efforts to implement Learning Management Systems (LMS) which can help the learning process become higher quality and larger scope [13]. The education sector is one of the most interesting cases to observe regarding the use of LMS tools [6]. Aspects that improve with the use of LMS tools include motivation, interest, commitment, focus on task, behavior, and much more [2].

In some cases, the contribution that LMS make to education could be counteracted by the lack of usability that they may have. A fluid learning process can be interrupted

because it is hard to understand the use of the tools that made this possible. When there are design problems, the user focus changes from trying to understand the content to understanding the use of the tool. There are two important variables to consider for the successful use of LMS - the quality of the information that should be transferred (education content of the platform) and shape and fluidness to transmit the message (interacting experience with the platform). Research by Westfall reported that 61% of surveyed people said that it was difficult to learn the use of the system [15].

Usability is a key factor to achieve user satisfaction. This includes the software being easy to use and learnable, through an interface that shows the content in an efficient format, simple and ordered; in this way, visual complexities would be avoided [11]. The measurement of usability has been considered one of the most difficult tasks because there is no standard model that covers all the necessary usability attributes [5].

Heuristic evaluation is one of the most used qualitative techniques to inspect software interfaces and find those problems that affect usability [4]. The importance of having a quantified level of usability makes it possible to explore comparisons between software products of the same type and makes it easier for companies to evaluate proposals to choose the best option [12]. Having a global score that identifies the usability level of an interface favors the recognition of the status of the website under study in terms of usability [3].

In this research, a framework that allows quantifying the level of usability and user experience based on the heuristic evaluation process is proposed. With foundations on a systematic review, this new approach developed for the assessment of platforms that support learning and teaching activities on university institutions, considers the main aspects that according to the literature are relevant in this domain. Likewise, an assessment procedure is formulated by contemplating the best practices that were identified.

2 A Systematic Literature Review

In order to identify those important key aspects that LMS should have, a systematic review was made. The purpose of identifying those aspects is to analyze them, systematize them, and to propose a framework based on the most important aspects identified.

The present systematic review was conducted based on the parameters defined by Kitchenham and Charters [10]. In this case, the activities to be performed are: definition of the research questions and search strategy, the selection of the primary studies, the extraction of the papers and the analysis of the results.

2.1 Research Questions

The main objective was to summarize some studies related to usability, user experience, learning management systems and usability evaluation methods. We used the PICOC table criteria in order to do this review according to the protocol established by Petticrew & Roberts [14]. In addition, we employed synonyms and related terms to find better results. These criteria are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. General concepts defined using the PICOC criteria.

Criterion	Description
Population	Web platforms that support learning
Intervention	Heuristic evaluation of usability and user experience
Comparison	Other methods of usability evaluation
Outcome	Case studies in which any method of usability evaluation is applied
Context	Academic and business context, including all types of stakeholders and empirical studies

Finally, the research questions are the following:

- **RQ1:** Which are the most relevant aspects of usability and user experience?
- **RQ2:** Which are the most important characteristics in learning management systems?
- **RQ3:** Which are the activities and characteristics of the usability evaluation models?
- **RQ4:** Which are the guidelines considered in other domains to evaluate usability?

2.2 Search Strategy

We defined our search strategy based on the general concepts. Some synonymous were selected to achieve a more comprehensive search. The search process was performed by using four recognized databases to search for primary studies: ACM Digital Library, IEEEExplore, SCOPUS, and SpringerLink. Grey literature was excluded since it is not peer-reviewed.

In this phase, the search chains or *queries* that were used in the search engines of each database were formulated. It is important to mention that the syntax of the queries could vary according to the database that is employed. After grouping a series of concepts using the connectors AND/OR, the resulting search string was:

("usability" OR "user experience" OR "UX" OR "HCI") AND ("heuristic" OR "heuristic evaluation" OR "usability evaluation" OR "model evaluation usability") AND ("quantify" OR "quantitative" OR "approach quantitative" OR "comparative" OR "comparative analysis" OR "methodology to evaluate usability" OR "quantify usability" OR "measure usability" OR "method to evaluate usability") AND ("interface" OR "software" OR "web" OR "system" OR "satisfaction" OR "characteristic" OR "guideline" OR "design" OR "methodology" OR "case study") AND ("elearning" OR "e-learning" OR "learning management system" OR "LMS" OR "education" OR "higher education" OR "university" OR "e-learning system" OR "web platform to teaching" OR "web platform" OR "web system to support teaching")

2.3 Search Process and Data Extraction

In order to determine if an article must be considered as relevant, we defined the following inclusion criteria: *the study should present a methodology, framework or study case in which the usability and user experience are evaluated.* In the same way, we defined the exclusion criteria: *in the study, the specialists do not apply a usability or user experience evaluation in an intangible product as a software.* The automated

search for our systematic mapping review was performed on October 20th, 2018. Table 2 shows the search results that were found. In addition, Table 3 shows the selected studies from the four databases used in this research. These studies were selected by discarding the studies that do not meet the inclusion criteria and present any of the exclusion criteria.

Table 2. Search Results for RQ1, RQ2, RQ3 and RQ4.

Database Name	Search Results	Duplicate Papers	Relevant Papers
ACM Digital Library	24	-	9
IEEEExplore	13	-	6
Scopus	36	4	7
SpringerLink	32	2	1
TOTAL	105	6	23

Table 3. Selected Primary Studies.

Study ID	Author Name	Year	Title
SS1	S. Hedegaard & J. G. Simonsen	2013	Extracting usability and user experience information from online user reviews
SS2	Auhood Al-Faries et al.	2013	Evaluating the accessibility and usability of top Saudi e-government services
SS3	A.L. Dias et al.	2014	HEUA: A Heuristic Evaluation with Usability and Accessibility requirements to assess Web systems
SS4	L. Hasan & K. T. Al-Sarayreh	2015	An Integrated Measurement Model for Evaluating Usability Attributes
SS5	M. Rush Hovde	2015	Effective user experience in online technical communication courses: employing multiple methods within organizational contexts to assess usability
SS6	J. Choma et al.	2016	Working beyond technical aspects: an approach for driving the usability inspection adding the perspective of user experience
SS7	D. Quiñones Otey	2017	A methodology to develop usability / user experience heuristics
SS8	K. Sagar & A. Saha	2017	Qualitative usability feature selection with ranking: a novel approach for ranking the identified usability problematic attributes for academic websites using data-mining techniques
SS9	L. Hasan	2018	Usability Problems on Desktop and Mobile Interfaces of the Moodle Learning Management System (LMS)
SS10	R. S. AlRoobaea et al.	2013	A framework for generating a domain specific inspection evaluation method: A comparative study on social networking websites
SS11	A. Gordillo et al.	2014	The usefulness of usability and user experience evaluation methods on an e-Learning platform development from a developer's perspective: A case study

SS12	M. R. H. Iman and A. Rasoolzadegan	2015	Quantitative evaluation of software usability with a fuzzy expert system
SS13	J. S. Mtebe & M. M. Kissaka	2015	Heuristics for evaluating usability of Learning Management Systems in Africa
SS14	Md Alamgir Kabir et al.	2016	An analytical and comparative study of software usability quality factors
SS15	T. Granollers	2016	Validación experimental de un conjunto heurístico para evaluaciones de UX de sitios web de comercio-e
SS16	M. Ivanović et al.	2013	Usability and privacy aspects of Moodle: students' and teachers' perspective
SS17	N. M. Sabri et al.	2013	A Quantitative Approach in the Usability Evaluation of a Courseware
SS18	R. Deraniyagala et al.	2015	Usability study of the EduMod eLearning Program for contouring nodal stations of the head and neck
SS19	I. S. Junus et al.	2015	Usability evaluation of the student centered e-Learning environment
SS20	B. Murillo et al.	2017	Usability testing as a complement of heuristic evaluation: A case study
SS21	D. W. A. B. Emang et al.	2017	Usability studies on E-Learning Platforms: Preliminary Study in USM
SS22	F. Paz et al.	2018	Quantifying the Usability Through a Variant of the Traditional Heuristic Evaluation Process
SS23	S. Sai Aparna & K. K. Baseer	2015	SIRIUS-WUEP: A Heuristic-Based Framework for Measuring and Evaluating Web Usability in Model-Driven Web Development

In addition, there were found some secondary studies applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria to references in the most relevant of the primary studies. These secondary studies are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Selected Secondary Studies.

Study ID	Author Name	Year	Title
SS24	K. Eason	1984	Towards the experimental study of usability
SS25	J. Nielsen	1993	Usability Engineering
SS26	ISO 9241-11	1998	Ergonomics requirements for office work with visual display terminals (VDTs) – Part 11: Guidance on usability
SS27	ISO/IEC 9126	2001	Software engineering – Product quality
SS28	T. Reeves et al.	2002	Usability and instructional design heuristics for e-learning evaluation
SS29	E. Folmer et al.	2003	A framework for capturing the relationship between usability and software architecture
SS30	A. Abran et al.	2003	Usability Meanings and Interpretations in ISO Standards
SS31	J. Rosato et al.	2004	Usability of course management systems by students

SS32	Mehlenbacher et al.	2005	Usable E-Learning: A conceptual model for evaluation and design
SS33	L. Dringus & M. Cohen	2005	An adaptable usability heuristic checklist for online courses
SS34	C. Ardito et al.	2005	An approach to usability evaluation of e-learning applications
SS35	A. Seffah et al.	2006	Usability measurement and metrics: A consolidated model
SS36	J. Nielsen	2006	Prioritizing Web Usability
SS37	N. Bevan	2008	Classifying and selecting UX and usability measures
SS38	P. Ketola & V. Roto	2008	Exploring user experience measurement needs
SS39	P. Zaharias & Poylymenakou	2009	Developing a usability evaluation method for e-learning applications: Beyond functional usability
SS40	M. Giannakos	2009	A combinational evaluation method of computer applications
SS41	HS Al-Khalifa	2010	Heuristic Evaluation of the usability of E-Government Websites: A Case from Saudi Arabia
SS42	Al-Sarrayrih et al.	2010	Evaluation of a Moodle based learning management system applied at Berlin institute of technology based on Iso-9126
SS43	M. Giannakos	2010	The evaluation of an e-learning web-based platform
SS44	ISO/IEC 25010	2011	Systems and software engineering – Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) – System and software quality models
SS45	P. Zaharias & Koutsabasis	2011	Heuristic evaluation of e-learning courses: a comparative analysis of two e-learning heuristic sets
SS46	B. Ghirardini	2011	E-learning methodologies. A guide for designing and developing e-learning courses
SS47	K. Dubey et al.	2012	Usability Evaluation of Object-Oriented Software System using Fuzzy Logic Approach
SS48	M. C. Suárez et al.	2013	Sirius: A heuristic-based framework for measuring web usability adapted to the type of website
SS49	L. Senol et al.	2014	Usability evaluation of a Moodle based learning management system
SS50	S. Thuseethan et al.	2014	Usability evaluation of learning management systems in Sri Lankan universities
SS51	D. Gupta & A. Ahlawat	2014	A critical analysis of a hierarchy-based usability model
SS52	F. Paz et al.	2015	Heuristic Evaluation as a Complement to Usability Testing: A Case Study in Web Domain
SS53	T. Issa	2015	Sustainable Design HCI, Usability and Environmental Concerns
SS54	H. Sharp et al.	2015	Interaction Design - Beyond Human-Computer Interaction
SS55	A. A. Samani	2015	Heuristic Evaluation of the Usability of LMS (Moodle) at EMU

2.4 Results

There were 18 papers that answer RQ1 (SS1, SS4, SS6, SS14, SS24, SS26, SS27, SS29, SS30, SS35, SS36, SS37, SS38, SS44, SS47, SS51, SS53, SS54). The usability/UX aspects that are used in the evaluation models according to the systematic review were extracted and are discussed in Section 3.1.

In the same way, to answer RQ2, 14 papers were selected (SS5, SS9, SS13, SS16, SS19, SS21, SS28, SS31, SS32, SS39, SS42, SS46, SS49, SS50). According to the authors, there are relevant design aspects that contribute to satisfy the learning objectives that are frequently requested by the educational institutions when they search for learning tools. The details are described in Section 3.1.

There were 11 papers that answer RQ3 (SS3, SS12, SS15, SS17, SS20, SS22, SS23, SS28, SS32, SS45, SS52). Some important strategies related to the process that must be followed in a usability/UX evaluation were obtained from these studies. These approaches were compared to decide how to establish the assessment framework. These methodologies are discussed in Section 3.2.

Finally, the RQ4 is related with the principles used in the heuristic evaluation models which allow to get the usability level - quantitatively or qualitatively - in the platforms from other domains, that can be used as well for learning support platforms. There were 18 papers that were used to answer this research question (SS2, SS3, SS7, SS8, SS10, SS11, SS18, SS23, SS25, SS28, SS32, SS33, SS34, SS40, SS41, SS43, SS48, SS55). The details are discussed in Section 3.2.

3 Framework Proposal

In this section, we present the results of the different proposed objectives. The first objective identify the most relevant aspects of LMS based on usability and user experience (UX), the second objective identify the current usability evaluation proposals that allow to evaluate the level of usability and user experience in the LMS; finally, the third objective proposes the quantitative evaluation from a list of verification items to measure usability and UX.

3.1 The most relevant aspects of LMS based on usability and UX

This first part answers the research question related to Which are the most relevant aspects of Usability and User experience? (RQ1) and Which are the most important characteristics in the learning management systems? (RQ2).

To identify the most relevant aspects, the usability evaluation models developed by researchers in the field and some international standards such as ISO 9241-11 [9], ISO/IEC 9126 [7] and ISO/IEC 25010 [8] were used. In addition, a process was defined that explains the obtaining of the relevant aspects.

In the first place, after the systematic review carried out, aspects of usability and user experience were collected. Then, a standardization process was applied to homogenize the aspects described by the authors, in order to consolidate those aspects repeated in the same label, which was useful to identify those aspects that appear most frequently

in the result of the systematic review and, in this way, a quantitative analysis could be carried out.

After that, the Pareto statistical principle [16] was applied in order to choose 20% of the 32 aspects found and thus obtain an objective perspective. This allowed obtaining 7 aspects; however, we found 3 other aspects that had the same frequency as the last one selected by Pareto, which were added at the end, adding 10 aspects finally. Table 5 shows the list of selected aspects.

Table 5. List of Usability and UX Selected Aspects.

ID	Aspect	Definition
1	Attractiveness	If the system is attractive to the user.
2	Effectiveness	Accuracy and integrity with which the user achieves the objective.
3	Efficiency	Resources - used in relation to accuracy and integrity - with which the user achieves his objectives.
4	Learnability	The ease with which the required characteristics can be mastered to achieve particular objectives.
5	Memorability	It is the ease with which it allows the user to remember the elements of the system.
6	Reliability	It refers to the error rate that the system can present.
7	Satisfaction	It is the ability of the software to satisfy users in a context of specific use.
8	Security	It is defined as the property in which the risks - with respect to hardware and software - can be neglected.
9	Universality	It determines if the software accommodates a diversity of users, regardless of the cultural differences that exist.
10	Utility	If the software product allows you to solve real problems in an acceptable way.

On the other side, to ensure that the selected aspects are adequate to elaborate the proposed framework of work, the expert judgment was used, which was carried out by 4 experts in the HCI and Education domain. In which the Likert scale was used to obtain a score for each of the aspects. Each aspect was averaged according to the scores assigned by the experts and it was established that those who did not pass the average; that is, having an average of a minimum score of 2, would be excluded from the selected aspects.

All the selected aspects obtained a score higher than the average, since the average score recorded - by aspect - was at least 3.25. With this, it is concluded that all the selected aspects should be included in the framework. Also, Effectiveness, Efficiency, and Learnability obtained a score of 4.

On the other hand, in order to ensure the desired impact on user learning, we sought to collect characteristics that assess whether a platform is usable and didactically suitable for learning. To achieve this result was made a new systematic review following the methodology of Kitchenham [10] with the purpose of finding research related to the field of learning and; after that, interviews were conducted with teachers from the Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú to strengthen what was found in the literature and

/ or add new features from the perspective of end users. Once the feature sets of literature and interviews were obtained, the next step was the union of these two together. The characteristics obtained by these two means are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Some Learning Characteristics Selected by the Literature and Interview.

ID	Some characteristics regarding content management systems for learning
1	Electronic advice by the tutors.
2	Virtual classes.
3	Communication between students and teachers.
4	Reliability and error recovery.
5	Knowledge and learning of the student regarding their abilities and experiences in the technologies.
6	Structured content of the system.
7	Student control over the use of the tool that supports the learning.
8	Development of individual and group activities.

Finally, this set of characteristics was evaluated by researchers, through an Expert Judgment to guarantee the election of these. Similar to Usability aspects, the Likert scale was used for the evaluation, so that the experts assign a score to each characteristic individually.

In the same way as the previous result, the expert judgment was carried out by 3 experts in the HCI and Education domain. Each aspect was averaged according to the scores assigned by the experts and all those who passed the average were selected. For this set of results, the higher score was obtained for these characteristics: social dynamics, such as the interaction between instructors and classmates; expression of opinions through surveys; comments on student assignments; integration with web tools; review of the progress of student evolution; and tasks and activities.

3.2 The current usability evaluation proposals

Next, the research is related to answer the question about Which are the activities and characteristics of the usability evaluation models? (RQ3) and Which are the activities and characteristics of the usability evaluation models? related to LMS. (RQ4).

This objective seeks to select those characteristics, criteria and / or guidelines of the proposals - found in the literature - that evaluate usability, in order to construct the scheme of the verification items.

Through the systematic review, we collected research on usability evaluation with both quantitative and qualitative approaches. To compare the found models, the following characteristics were considered:

- Usability evaluation methods.
- Heuristics or guidelines, in case it is a Heuristic Evaluation.
- The flow or process followed to carry out the evaluation.
- Characteristics found and resources used, as people involved (experts and/or users).
- Qualitative or quantitative approach of the applied usability evaluation method.
- Factors considered in the formula, in this case, a quantitative approach.

After making a mapping for each evaluation model found by the systematic review, those characteristics that could be adapted with greater precision to the domain of the present project were selected, as shown in Table 7.

Table 7. List of Characteristics.

ID	Activity
1	The heuristics or aspects to evaluate will present good coverage and distribution. However, the verification items must have minimal redundancy.
2	The verification items will consider aspects of usability and characteristics of content management for learning, in order to improve the user experience.
3	The verification items will be grouped by categories.
4	The evaluation score will be in the range of 0 - 100.
5	The general score will be calculated through an average between the categories of the verification items.
6	Each category will be assigned a weight that represents its importance with respect to the others.
7	The verification items will have answers of more than one type. For example: Likert scale, Y / N.
8	The number of evaluators will be a variable within the formula to determine the degree of usability.
9	The verification items will be the most atomic possible so that the results of the evaluation present less uncertainty.
10	The score of each category will be calculated through an average of the results of the verification items that comprise it.

Likewise, to increase the effectiveness of the proposal, we sought guidelines from other domains that are related to education and usability that can be adopted to this research. The process of obtaining the guidelines was through a systematic review of the literature, with which to find relevant research for this stage.

Next, the guidelines found were listed, in order to move on to the standardization process, since many guidelines referred to the same context. Finally, a total of 25 standardized guidelines were obtained, with which it will be possible to evaluate the usability for some characteristics of the LMS. Table 8 shows those guidelines.

Table 8. List of Selected Guidelines.

ID	Guideline	ID	Guideline	ID	Guideline
1	Accessibility	10	Content organization	19	Effectiveness of teaching
2	Efficiency	11	Feedback	20	Adequate structure
3	Relationship between the system and the real world	12	Control and freedom of apprentices	21	Use of comprehensive language
4	Aesthetic appeal	13	Message design	22	Support for learning
5	Bug prevention	14	Help and documentation	23	Design and consistency
6	Media integration	15	Navigation	24	Resources
7	Communication protocols	16	Visibility and system status	25	Reliability and functionality

8	Instructional evaluation	17	Security		
9	Memorability	18	Interactivity		

3.3 The list of verification items to measure usability and UX

In this section, the proposal that was carried out is shown; that is, the list of verification items that will allow to quantify the level of usability in support platforms for learning.

To calculate the degree of usability, some proposals found by the systematic review were considered, such as Bonastre & Granollers [1] and Paz [12]. With these findings, the authors concluded that the measurement of the degree of usability in the platforms will be made as follows:

$$NUC = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^{10} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{10} x_{ijk} \right) \right)}{n}$$

Where:

- NUC: Quantized Usability Level
- n: Number of evaluators
- i: Evaluator "i"
- j: Category "j"
- k: Check item "k" of Category
- x_{ijk} : Score of the check item "k" of Category "j" of the evaluator "i"

After mapping the results obtained previously, a total of 100 verification items could be constructed. This list is grouped into a total of 10 categories: General Aspects, Information and Identity, Structure and Navigability, Functions and Security, Support and Documentation, Interaction between Students and Teachers, Materials and Resources, Individual and Collaborative Activities, Evaluations and Feedback, and finally, Environment and Quality of learning. Of which, half focuses on usability issues and the other half on learning. Likewise, each category has an equal number of questions, so there is a total of 10 verification items per category.

This checklist has a scoring system 0 - 100, with score 0 the lowest and score 100 the highest. With respect to the verification items, these are presented in the form of affirmative sentences from a positive approach, since the aim is to obtain the ideal level of usability.

The verification items are of two types: on the one hand, for the direct answers, alternatives of "yes" and "no" are counted, which are equivalent to 3 points and 0 points, respectively. On the other hand, the other types of check items - for subjective answers - their alternatives are subject to a Likert - 4 scale, where the score is distributed as follows: "Totally disagree" equals 0 points; "Disagree", 1 point; "Agree", 2 points; and finally, "Totally agree", 3 points. Next, a set of checklists that evaluate aspects of Usability and User Experience (UX) are presented in Table 9. In the same way, a set of checklist is presented that evaluates aspects related to learning in Table 10.

Table 9. Checklist of General Aspects Category – Usability/UX.

ID	Items	Score
1	The objectives of the platform are concrete and well defined.	TD D A TA
2	You easily find the functions and options that you want when you interact with the tool.	TD D A TA
3	The platform provides ease for the user to enter/modify information.	TD D A TA
4	The user has control over the platform.	TD D A TA
5	The cognitive load is minimized by providing familiarity in the sequence of actions of a process.	TD D A TA
6	The platform presents a language without jargon.	TD D A TA
7	The representations of icons or elements used are related to real-world concepts (e.g., the symbol to save looks like a floppy disk)	TD D A TA
8	The platform displays messages/warning notifications that prevent the occurrence of errors.	TD D A TA
9	You can customize the language of the content of the platform.	TD D A TA
10	The platform can be used by those users with a physical disability (e.g., color blind).	TD D A TA

Table 10. Checklist of "Materials and Resources" Category - Learning.

ID	Items	Score
1	The files are easy to upload and download from the platform.	TD D A TA
2	Learning objects can be created and reused easily.	TD D A TA
3	The language used is appropriate, because it uses terms, expressions, and ideas that are similar to those used in my academic environment.	TD D A TA
4	The materials provided are not confusing and motivate the interest of the student.	TD D A TA
5	The images, audios and/or videos provide an added value to learning.	TD D A TA
6	The materials in PDF format can be viewed in the same window as in a new one.	N Y
7	The platform has a digital library.	N Y
8	It has resources such as audios, videos, images, among others, to encourage learning.	N Y
9	The repositories of materials/resources are available for any user.	N Y
10	The materials and/or resources are related to the topics that address the course.	N Y

Fig. 1. Framework to evaluate the usability/UX of Learning Support Platforms.

Based on the information that was collected and analyzed from the literature, a preliminary framework to quantify the level of usability and user experience of Learning Support Platforms (LMS) was proposed. The structure of this proposal is presented in Figure 1. In this image, the authors highlight the evaluation process that was defined as well as the usability, UX and educational aspects that are covered by the checklist. The new framework is intended to be used by both, expert specialists in the area of Human-Computer Interaction and the educational domain. The reason to propose the use of the framework in this way, is because of this type of professionals can perform a more in-depth analysis and evaluation of the usability/UX and learning aspects of these systems. With basis on a predefined set of characteristics and following a well-structured process, the experts can perform a more efficient assessment. However, more study cases and experimentations are required to consolidate the new proposal.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

The usability, as well as the UX, have become critical aspects to be considered in the development of software products. Nowadays, these quality attributes represent the main concerns of the software industries, since ensuring a high level of ease of use and UX in the applications, leads to establish an environment of appropriate use for the interaction with the system. The new paradigm in the software development is not only about providing the users with a tool to achieve their goals but also to ensure that the user experience is quality enough to generate satisfaction on the end user.

The systematic literature review has allowed to identify the most relevant aspects in both usability as learning, that must be considered in the design of interfaces for learning support platforms. Additionally, this review allowed to find characteristics that help

to quantify the level usability and UX, and some heuristics or guidelines related to domain of study. Based on these results, a preliminary framework to measure the level of usability and UX has been proposed.

The preliminary framework consists of a checklist with 100 items. Unlike to questionnaires or the software metrics, this proposed saves resources like both time-consuming and a considerable number of evaluators. Some items of verification have a scale Likert 4, since this prevents the evaluator to choose an intermediate option so that the accuracy of the proposed framework is not affected.

This proposal does not deal to replace SUS or SUPR-Q or another questionnaire for the usability evaluation and UX. The present is a proposal extracted with basis on the information revised from the literature and it is a first approach with which is still necessary to carry out tests, case studies and numerical experimentation to validate its effectiveness in practice.

The authors of this paper suggest applying the results obtained in a particular case study, so that the criteria of the proposed framework can be validated. The analysis of the results should also be considered in depth, taking into account that the criteria detailed in this paper are orientated to LMS for university education. This study is intended to demonstrate that the proposed framework can be reliable and efficient for stakeholders through obtaining quantitative results.

This framework is a preliminary version that has been established based on the data collected in the literature, and the final proposal is intended to be a future work.

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